

Oxidation of Ce(III) by Acid Bromate

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The reaction of Ce(III) sulphate with KBrO_3 in sulphuric acid has been followed potentiometrically. The results are consistent with the mechanism proposed by Noyes, Field and Koros.

THE data on redox potential of half cells involving oxybromine species as well as Ce(IV)/Ce(III) led Noyes, Field and Koros¹ to derive certain conclusions regarding the reaction between Ce(III) and BrO_3^- in aqueous solution. The kinetics of this reaction was studied qualitatively by Kasperek and Bruce² and later by Field, Thomson and Noyes⁴. According to the latter investigators, Ce(III) and other weak one electron reducing agents like Mn(II), Np(V), etc. do not react directly with HBrO_3 but they reduce BrO_3^- formed as an intermediate through a sequence which leads to an autocatalytic production of HBrO_3 . The E° values and Latimer's¹ free energy data of the bromine and oxybromine species as well as Ce(IV)/Ce(III) systems are unfavourable to this reaction, and the table of potentials^{1,2} also reveals that BrO_3^- can reduce Ce(IV) so that the reaction may be expressed more precisely as

Thus, if Ce(III) ions are present in large concentrations the reaction may be pushed forward particularly in view of the decreased potential of the Ce(IV)/Ce(III) in H_2SO_4 media. Previous authors³ worked with very low concentrations of Ce(III) and with $5.85 \times 10^{-5} M$ Ce(III) initially taken, the amount of Ce(IV) formed was only $3.21 \times 10^{-5} M$ [a maximum of 55% consumption of Ce(III)]. In view of this uncertainty of the stoichiometry and the theoretical possibilities of stepwise reduction of bromate, we proposed to study the mechanism of this reaction potentiometrically.

Experimental

The stock solution (0.04 M) of cerous sulphate (S. Merck) and (0.0625 M) bromate were prepared in boiled out distilled water adjusting the sulphuric acid concentrations. The sulphuric acid concentration was varied from 0.5 N to 6.0 N.

Among the products, bromine was identified by its yellow colour, pungent smell and also chemically by KI and starch iodide paper. Reaction mixtures in various proportions were prepared in separate vessels, brought to equilibrium and potentials recorded by the saturated calomel—Pt electrode combination method. Reactions were not fast at ordinary temperature, so the systems were heated to

60° for about 3 hr to reach equilibrium. The equilibrium state of the system was ascertained by the steady potentials developed at the platinum electrode.

Results and Discussion

The accompanying graphs represent the variation of e.m.f. against volume of the added reagent. The Tables 1, 2 and 3 contain the molar ratios in which the oxidation-reduction occurs. These are derived from the inflexions in the curves. The results show that when Ce(III) solution is added to an excess (fixed volume) of bromate the reduction of the latter occurs in two steps (meaning one stable intermediate) corresponding to inflexions at 4.0 and 5.0 moles of Ce(III)/ BrO_3^- . In the reverse case, however, there is only one inflexion at 4.0 moles of Ce(III)/ BrO_3^- . The results were unchanged on altering the concentrations of the mineral acid used. In each case, bromine could be visibly detected as one of the products. Since cerous ion is not likely to react with bromate directly at an appreciable rate, it is supposed that the presence of traces of Br^- ion in the solution initiates the autocatalytic production of HBrO_3 which may carry the redox process in accordance with the mechanism suggested by Noyes *et al*².

Since Br^- ion concentration is too small in the system, $\text{BrO}_3^- - \text{Br}^-$ reaction leading to bromine will not occur. The E° for HOBr/Br^- couple on calculation is found to be 1.33 volt. This makes the E° of the reaction (2) also unfavourable. But calculations on the basis of the Nernst equation :

$$E = E^\circ - \frac{RT}{nF} \log \frac{[\text{HBrO}_3][\text{HOBr}]}{[\text{BrO}_3^-][\text{Br}^-][\text{H}^+]^2}$$

would show a positive E (not E°) if we substitute the steady state concentrations of HBrO_3 and HOBr , as calculated from the Noyes formula,

$$[\text{HBrO}_3] = 5 \times 10^{-10} [\text{BrO}_3^-][\text{H}^+]$$

which makes the ratio of the numerator to denominator much less than one. This justifies postulating reaction (2).

TABLE 1—OXIDATION OF Ce(III) BY BROMATE

H ₂ SO ₄ (approx.)	Vessel contains 10 ml M/250 cerous ion and M/240 bromate solution added*		Vessel contains 10 ml M/320 bromate and M/25 cerous ion solution added**				Remarks
	Point of inflexion in ml	Molar ratio BrO ₃ ⁻ /Ce(III)	Point of inflexion in ml		Molar ratio Ce(III)/BrO ₃ ⁻		
			1st	2nd	1st	2nd	
0.5 N	2.4	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	Temperature 32°. Period of storage 24 hr. Heated at 60° in an electric oven for 2-3 hr. Colour change.
1 N	2.4	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	
1.5 N	2.4	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	
3 N	2.4	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	
6 N	2.4	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	
6 N	2.4	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	

* Colourless to pale yellow.

** Pale yellow to bright yellow.

TABLE 2—OXIDATION OF Ce(III) BY BROMATE

H ₂ SO ₄ (approx.)	Vessel contains 10 ml M/500 cerous ion and M/480 bromate solution added*		Vessel contains 10 ml M/640 bromate and M/25 cerous ion solution added**				Remarks
	Point of inflexion in ml	Molar ratio BrO ₃ ⁻ /Ce(III)	Point of inflexion in ml		Molar ratio Ce(III)/BrO ₃ ⁻		
			1st	2nd	1st	2nd	
0.5 N	2.4	0.25	1.56	1.96	4	5	Temperature 32°. Period of storage 24 hr. Heated at 60° in an electric oven for 2-3 hr. Colour change.
1 N	2.4	0.25	1.56	1.96	4	5	
1.5 N	2.4	0.25	1.56	1.96	4	5	
3 N	2.4	0.25	1.56	1.96	4	5	
6 N	2.4	0.25	1.56	1.96	4	5	
6 N	2.4	0.25	1.56	1.96	4	5	

* Colourless to pale yellow.

** Pale yellow to bright yellow.

TABLE 3—OXIDATION OF Ce(III) BY BROMATE

H ₂ SO ₄ (approx.)	Vessel contains 10 ml M/1000 cerous ion and M/640 bromate solution added*		Vessel contains 10 ml M/640 bromate and M/50 cerous ion solution added**				Remarks
	Point of inflexion in ml	Molar ratio BrO ₃ ⁻ /Ce(III)	Point of inflexion in ml		Molar ratio Ce(III)/BrO ₃ ⁻		
			1st	2nd	1st	2nd	
0.5 N	1.6	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	Temperature 32°. Period of storage 24 hr. Heated at 60° in an electric oven for 2-3 hr. Colour change.
1 N	1.6	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	
1.5 N	1.6	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	
3 N	1.6	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	
6 N	1.6	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	
6 N	1.6	0.25	3.12	3.92	4	5	

* Colourless to pale yellow.

** Pale yellow to bright yellow.

Now Noyes *et al* have given the following kinetic scheme of the autocatalytic production of HBrO₂ :

With the concentrations of bromate used in our reaction (Table 1 ; Fig. 1) the steady state concentration of HBrO₂ calculated from Noyes^{3,4} formula is of the order of 10⁻¹¹ M, a value too small to produce any inflexion in the curve. But the couple HBrO₂/HOBr with its E° = 1.74 volt is strong enough to oxidise Ce(III) to Ce(IV) through the reaction

This would require a net consumption of four moles of Ce(III) per mole of bromate. Thus HBrO₂ formed during this reaction acts as an autocatalyst to promote BrO₃⁻-Ce³⁺ reaction whereby bromate is converted to HOBr. The first inflexion in the curve (Fig. 1) is justified in this way.

With HOBr/Br₂ couple having E° = 1.57 volt, HOBr can further be reduced to bromine by another mole of Ce(III).

In the reverse case [inflexion of 0.25 mole of BrO₃⁻/Ce(III)] the reaction stops at the HOBr stage which is not unlikely in view of the sufficiently reducing environment in the system.

At lower concentrations of bromate ($10^{-2} M$), the graph is smooth and regular, while at higher concentration ($10^{-1} M$) the graph is marked with some erratic points after the first inflexion. This is due to the formation of $HBrO_2$, BrO_2 , etc. as intermediates in the interaction of $HOBr$ and BrO_2^- whereby several redox couples might be setting up and asserting themselves at the platinum electrode.

Fig. 1. 10 ml of $M/640 KBrO_3$ solution in $x(N) H_2SO_4$ taken in the cell.

Fig. 2. 10 ml of $M/250 Ce(III)$ solution $x(N) H_2SO_4$ taken in the cell.

References

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